

Fluoarsenates and Their Analogies with Sulphates. Part III*. Stability of Fluoarsenate Ion and its Comparison with Fluophosphate Ion

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Stabilities of fluophosphates and fluoarsenates have been measured by the method of Bjerrum and compared. K values of the reaction:

(where X = P or As) have been found as 5.2 and 5.61. Stabilities of these two complex acids have been found to be of the same order.

From our study of the various compounds (simple, double, and basic) of fluoarsenates (*Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1956, 285, 92; this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 805) of bivalent metals, these appear to be as stable as the corresponding fluophosphates. A study of the stabilities of these ions has therefore been deemed desirable. The present paper describes the comparison of the stabilities of the fluophosphates and fluoarsenates in solution.

The principle utilised in the study is the theoretical relationship outlined by Bjerrum ("Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", Haase and Son, 1941) in the change of pH due to complex formation on a statistical basis involving all the possible intermediate stages in a reversible manner. These relationships are not restricted to complex formation only, but may be applied to any equilibrium process regardless of the nature of the reacting substances.

For this study, the dissociation constants of H_3AsO_4 , H_3FO_4 , and HF having been considered necessary were determined following the method of Bjerrum by plotting $\bar{n}$ against the pH values of the solutions resulting from progressive addition of standard acid to solution of known strength of normal salts of either H_3AsO_4 or H_3FO_4 and anhydrous NaF.

* Part II : This *Journal*, 1960, 37, 805.

Decompositions of Monofluorophosphate and Monofluoroarsenate Ions in Aqueous Solution

The above ions may be assumed to react with acid in aqueous solution in the following manner:

where X stands for P or As. The respective equilibrium constants are :

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{HXO}_3\text{F}]^-}{[\text{XO}_3\text{F}]^{2-} [\text{H}^+]}$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{XO}_4] [\text{HF}]}{[\text{HXO}_3\text{F}]^- [\text{H}^+]}$$

K_1 and K_2 were determined in the following way as the reactions took place in a stepwise manner.

The pH values were measured at successive stages when a standard acid was added progressively to solutions of the salts of known strength.

If C represents the molar concentration of $[\text{XO}_3\text{F}]^{2-}$ originally taken, C_0 , that of $[\text{XO}_3\text{F}]^{2-}$ at equilibrium, and C_1 , that of $[\text{HXO}_3\text{F}]^-$ at equilibrium.

$\therefore C = C_0 + C_1 + \text{H}_3\text{XO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{XO}_4^- + \text{HXO}_4^{2-}$ (for all purposes XO_4^{2-} has not been taken into consideration).

$$C = C_0 + C_1 + \text{F}^- + \text{HF}.$$

$$A \text{ (acid added)} = C_1 + \text{H}_3\text{XO}_4 + \text{HF} - \text{HXO}_4^{2-} - \text{OH}^- + \text{H (acid left)}.$$

$$A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H (acid consumed)} = \text{H}_3\text{XO}_4 + \text{HF} - \text{HXO}_4^{2-} + C_1.$$

There are two possible cases depending on the relative values of $(A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H})$ and C .

(1) $C > A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H}$ where reaction (2) above is considered not to have taken place when $C = C_0 + C_1$.

$$A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H} = C_1$$

and

$$K_1 = \frac{C_1}{C_0 \times [\text{H}^+]} = \frac{[A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H}]}{[C - (A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H})] [\text{H}^+]}$$

(2) $A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H} > C$, when C_0 is considered to be zero, where

$$C = C_1 + \text{H}_3\text{XO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{XO}_4^- + \text{HXO}_4^{2-}$$

$$C = C_1 + \text{F}^- + \text{HF}$$

$$A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H} = \text{HF} + \text{H}_3\text{XO}_4 - \text{HXO}_4^{2-} + C_1 \quad \dots (3)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{XO}_4] [\text{HF}]}{[\text{H}^+] C_1}$$

and from the knowledge of the first two dissociation constants of H_3XO_4 (k' and k'') and that of HF (k_1)

$$= \frac{[\text{H}^+] [C - C_1]^2}{C_1(k' + \text{H})(k_1 + \text{H})}$$

where $C_1 = (A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H}) \text{HF} - \text{H}_3\text{XO}_4 \left(\frac{1 - k'k''}{\text{H}^2} \right)$ from (3)

$$= \frac{C [2\text{H}^2 + \text{H}(k_1k')] - (A + \text{OH}^- - \text{H})(k_1 + \text{H})(k' + \text{H})}{\text{H}^2 - k_1k'}$$

Overall Stability or Decomposition Constant

From the stepwise decompositions of $[\text{XO}_3\text{F}]^{2-}$ by progressive addition of acids, the overall equation becomes (adding eqns. 1 and 2)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{where } K(\text{overall}) &= \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{XO}_4][\text{HF}]}{[\text{XO}_3\text{F}]^{2-}[\text{H}^+]^2} \\ &= \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{XO}_4][\text{HF}]}{[\text{HXO}_3\text{F}]^-[\text{H}^+]} \times \frac{[\text{HXO}_3\text{F}]^-}{[\text{H}^+][\text{XO}_3\text{F}]^{2-}} \\ &= K_1K_2. \end{aligned}$$

Now from the above values we can calculate the constant for the following reaction as shown :

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$$K_b(\text{hydrolytic}) = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{XO}_4]^- [\text{F}^-]}{[\text{XO}_3\text{F}]^{2-}}$$

which can be broken up and written as

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{XO}_4][\text{HF}]}{[\text{XO}_3\text{F}]^{2-}[\text{H}^+]^2} \cdot \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{H}_2\text{XO}_4]^-}{[\text{H}_3\text{XO}_4]} \cdot \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{F}^-]}{[\text{HF}]} \\ &= K_1K_2k_1k'. \end{aligned}$$

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydrogen-ion concentrations were measured with a Phillips pH-meter, model No. GM 4491 using a quinhydrone electrode and a saturated calomel electrode. Glass portions of the electrodes were coated with paraffin. A polyethylene beaker was used as the titration vessel. For uniform mixing of the reacting liquids, a paraffin-coated electric stirrer was used. All solutions were prepared using a molar potassium chloride solution. While titrating, sufficient quantity of quinhydrone was added to the solutions.

$\text{K}_2\text{AsO}_3\text{F}$ was prepared as described previously (*loc. cit.*, 1956). $\text{K}_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}$ was prepared as described by Boothe ("Inorganic Synthesis", Vol. II, pp. 155-56, 1946). All other reagents used were of AnalaR quality.

TABLE I

Dissociation constants.

	H_3PO_4	H_3AsO_4	HF
k'	1×10^{-8}	1.1×10^{-8}	
k''	4×10^{-7}	2.0×10^{-7}	
k_1	...	..	3.16×10^{-4}

TABLE II
Dissociation studies of $K_2[PO_3F]$ and $K_2[AsO_3F]$.

A.	H.	C.	C ₁ .	C ₀ .	K ₁ .	K ₂ .	Mean.
A. $K_2PO_3F = 0.0119M$. $HCl = 0.5M$.							
4.90×10^{-4}	1.45×10^{-7}	1.180×10^{-3}	5.2×10^{-4}	1.13×10^{-3}	1.6×10^5		
9.90×10^{-4}	3.53×10^{-7}	1.175×10^{-3}	1.2×10^{-3}	1.08×10^{-3}	1.3×10^5		
1.49×10^{-3}	6.10×10^{-7}	1.170×10^{-3}	1.5×10^{-3}	1.03×10^{-3}	1.2×10^5		
2.50×10^{-3}	9.50×10^{-7}	1.165×10^{-3}	2.5×10^{-3}	9.30×10^{-3}	1.4×10^5		
3.50×10^{-3}	1.62×10^{-6}	1.160×10^{-3}	3.5×10^{-3}	8.30×10^{-3}	1.3×10^5		
3.90×10^{-3}	2.04×10^{-6}	1.150×10^{-3}	3.9×10^{-3}	7.90×10^{-3}	1.2×10^5		2.66×10^5
2.15×10^{-3}	6.16×10^{-3}	1.140×10^{-3}	1.03×10^{-3}	1.04×10^{-3}		6.16	
2.38×10^{-3}	$8.1^0 \times 10^{-3}$	1.130×10^{-3}	9.8×10^{-4}	1.03×10^{-3}		5.55	
2.60×10^{-3}	$9.8^0 \times 10^{-3}$	1.125×10^{-3}	9.7×10^{-4}	1.02×10^{-3}		5.12	5.61
B. $K_2AsO_3F = 0.01025M$. $HCl = 0.5M$							
$5.9^0 \times 10^{-4}$	9.33×10^{-8}	1.024×10^{-3}	5.90×10^{-4}	9.65×10^{-3}	6.5×10^5		
$9.9^0 \times 10^{-4}$	1.32×10^{-7}	1.023×10^{-3}	9.90×10^{-4}	9.24×10^{-3}	8.1×10^5		
1.49×10^{-3}	1.74×10^{-7}	1.022×10^{-3}	1.49×10^{-3}	8.73×10^{-3}	9.8×10^5		
3.47×10^{-3}	7.08×10^{-7}	1.018×10^{-3}	3.47×10^{-3}	6.71×10^{-3}	7.3×10^5		
4.90×10^{-3}	1.78×10^{-6}	1.015×10^{-3}	4.90×10^{-3}	5.25×10^{-3}	5.24×10^5		7.40×10^5
2.38×10^{-3}	9.55×10^{-3}	9.760×10^{-3}	1.62×10^{-3}	8.74×10^{-3}		2.00	
2.60×10^{-3}	1.10×10^{-3}	9.700×10^{-3}	1.46×10^{-3}	8.25×10^{-3}		2.22	
2.82×10^{-3}	1.35×10^{-3}	9.670×10^{-3}	1.17×10^{-3}	8.50×10^{-3}		2.31	2.18
				$K_2PO_3F.$		$K_2AsO_3F.$	
Overall const. $K = K_1K_2$				1.49×10^6		1.61×10^6	
Hydrolytic const. $K_h = K_1K_2K_3K'$				5.2		5.61	